

SEMIOTIC SIGNIFICANCE OF THE CONCEPT OF BEHAVIOUR

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Alimammedova Khabiba Rustamovna

*Lecturer, Department of Foreign Languages
Tashkent University of Information Technologies*

Abstract: *This article discusses the semiotic significance of the concept of behaviour. The opinions of several scholars on the subject are also cited.*

Key words: *human behaviour, semiotic, semiotics, concept, semiotic significance*

Behaviour can be described by verb combinations containing a perceptual-evaluative, sign component, but the verbs in these combinations can be very different in semantics. Verbs of speech and gestures, by virtue of their semantics, easily acquire semiotic behavioural significance. However, in addition, the verbalization of the BEHAVIOUR concept also occurs through verbs that do not have such "behavioural" characteristics in their systemic, dictionary semantics and are far from any semiotic actions. They also "willingly" turn into predicates of behaviour in a certain context, pointing to the "semiotization of the personality - its speech and behavioural manifestations" [1]

Semiotics is an investigation into how meaning is created and how meaning is communicated. Its origins lie in the academic study of how signs and symbols (visual and linguistic) create meaning.

The most general definition of semiotics is the science of signs (Gr.sēmēion - sign, sign) and languages. Semiotics studies signs and sign systems as a tool for creating, transmitting and storing information, that is, as a medium that links into a single chain our consciousness, languages and the reality in which we exist. As a field of science and academic discipline, semiotics continues to be in its infancy and self-determination. This is confirmed a number of problematic issues.[2]

It is a way of seeing the world, and of understanding how the landscape and culture in which we live has a massive impact on all of us unconsciously.

Semiotics is a key tool to ensure that the person on the receiving end unambiguously understands intended meanings (of for instance a piece of communication or a new product). [3] Usually there are good reasons if someone doesn't understand the real intention of a message and semiotics can help unravel that confusion, ensuring clarity of meaning.

In the Encyclopaedic Dictionary of Culture of the 20th Century, V. Rudnev defines semiotics as one of the most specific interdisciplinary areas of our time,

without, however, clarifying the essence of this specifics. From my point of view, the peculiarity of semiotics stems from an ontologically indeterminate research subject and absolutely boundless boundaries that do not allow to accurately outline her area of interest.

Semiotics started out as an academic investigation of the meaning of words (linguistics), it moved into examining people's behaviour (anthropology and psychology), then evolved to become an enquiry into culture and society (sociology and philosophy), following that it moved onto assisting with analyses of cultural products (films, literature, art - critical theory), and finally and more recently became a methodology for researching and analysing consumer behaviour and brand communications.

The semiotic significance of behaviour is expressed in the fact that in the linguistic picture of the world there are numerous cases of transformation of various gestures, speech actions, body movements, movements of facial muscles, as well as actions that do not have pronounced sign-behavioural characteristics, into behavioural acts, as evidenced by a variety of verb in the context of some adverbs of mode of action. Such adverbs are markers of the semiotic significance of behaviour.

Behavioural symptoms are signs for interpreting and evaluating the behaviour itself as such and externalized from the inner world of the subject of his relationship to the environment, as a rule, the social world.

Compare the following statements:

After replacing the receiver she sat down on the edge of the coffee table and smiled to herself

*He smiled **effusively**, gave a mock bow, and went to stand beside one of the thrones.*

These examples of the use of the verb smile in various contexts convincingly demonstrate the fundamental difference in the interpretation of mimic action. As is known, the central feature of action predicates is the feature of controllability with the entire set of aspects of the controlled action that accompany or determine this feature: intentionality, purposefulness, awareness, etc. [4].

Although the verb smile does not belong to the central action verbs (like physical action verbs such as cut, wash, paint, etc.), to smile means to consciously move the muscles of the face in a certain way:

to raise the corners of your mouth when you are happy, pleased, or being friendly, or when you think something is funny.

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